

IMPACT ON HR PRACTICES ON THE EMPLOYEE'S PERFORMANCE: A STUDY IN PRIVATE BANKING SECTOR

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Abstract

Human Resource is base for every organization because in absence of manpower an organization cannot run. As banks are based on the performance of their employees and their performance is linked with the human resource practices provided by their banks for their growth and development in this sector. So it is necessary for every bank to provide them better practices so that banks can stand in this competitive environment. Human resource practises are essentially the levers that enable the development of a pool of human capital. Businesses require a distinct set or bundle of human resource practises to support their distinct cultures and objectives. Human resource strategies shown to be most predictive of business performance when combined with a participatory structure that encourages workers to devote discretionary effort toward beneficial organisational outcomes. The main purpose of the study is to overview various HR practices affecting the employees performance and to measure the impact of the HR practices on the employees performance. This Descriptive study is based on the sample of employee's workings in different banks. The data was collected by using questionnaire (Google form) The sample method used for the study was purposive sampling – 250 samples have been taken from the private sector banks in the study area. The study concluded that practices of HR such as Training and Development, Employee Engagement, Competence, Recognition, Leadership and Compensation are directly influencing the performance of the employees. It is suggested that the management may focus on these practices much as they contribute more on their employees' performance.

Keywords

HR Practices; Perceived Employee Performance and Banking Sector.

1. Introduction - HRM and Banking Industry

The Indian banking sector, particularly commercial banks, has come to appreciate the critical need of a strong human resource emphasis in order to thrive in the face of a quickly changing environment, global competition, and other impending challenges. With attrition

becoming a harsh reality in the Indian banking business, it is becoming evident that organisational interventions must be used to create employee loyalty rather than allowing it to emerge naturally. In this environment, it is necessary to consider developing workforce-related human resource policies and processes. Human resources are the most valuable and vital

component of every business's ability to operate smoothly, effectively, and efficiently. Firms are considered competitive in today's era, when the world has become a global village, only on the basis of their human resource capability (Fatima et al, 2011). To accomplish an organization's goals and objectives, it is necessary to have highly qualified and talented employees. Historically, human beings were viewed as a tool whose behaviour could be regulated for the benefit of the enterprise and replaced as needed, according to the concept of people management. Additionally, the company's regulations were more rigid and the organisation was more centralised. However, with the development of the concept of human resource management (HRM), which is more compatible with biological systems and possesses a cross-cultural and cross-hierarchical structure. Adaptability and dispersion of organisations are increasing. Human resource management conducts an in-depth examination of the entire organisation.

Human resource management is crucial for organisations to accomplish their goals and maintain a competitive advantage. Human resource management procedures are organisational actions aimed at managing the organization's pool of human resources and ensuring that those resources are utilised effectively to accomplish corporate goals¹. Human resource management approaches refer to the activities, policies, and processes involved in planning, acquiring, developing, utilising, assessing, and maintaining the appropriate quantity and skill mix of workers to accomplish the organization's goals. Banking is a critical component of India's financial services industry². The sound financial system has

enabled continued expansion, resulting in long-term economic growth. The Indian banking sector is attempting to reconcile international best practises in human resource management with indigenous norms and sensibilities. Human resource management departments in banks are increasingly being recognised as key business partners in charge of critical corporate resources. The HR function is expected to aid the business in becoming more agile by using strategies that enable it to not only adapt to but also profit from external environment changes. Ascertain that human resources are utilised effectively within the organisation and that they are integrated to all other business resources³.

Any organization's success is contingent upon competent, effective, and well-communicated human resource and commercial processes, as well as compliance with applicable laws and regulations. In truth, prudent planning and the establishment of effective systems significantly ease regulatory compliance. Bank activity in India has expanded considerably during the last three decades. Banks' business profiles have evolved significantly away from traditional banking activities and toward non-traditional ones such as merchant banking, mutual funds, innovative financial services and products, and human resource development. Banks view product creation and differentiation, innovation and customisation, cost containment, cross-selling, and technological improvement as critical components of their retail business's success. As a result, banks have begun to understand the critical role of human resources in client interactions.

¹ Azad, M. R., Khan, W., and Ahmed, A.A., (2011). HR Practices in Banking Sector on Perceived Employee Performance: A Case of Bangladesh, Eastern University Journal, 3(3), pp: 30-39.

² Guest D. (2002). "Human Resource Management Corporate Performance Employee WelibeiDg:

Building the Worker into HRM", The Journal of Industrial Relations, Vol. 44, pp. 335-358.

³ Perez, D.P., & Falcon, M.J. (2004). "The Influence of Human Resource Management Saving Bank Performance", The Service Industries Journal; Vol. 24, pp. 51-66.

2. The Indian Banking Sector's Challenges

Human resource management is a management function that entails the acquisition of acceptable human resources, their training, and development. Encourage them. Reward them effectively and instil in them a desire to be a member of the management team whose mission should be to provide focused, committed services to the organization's success and growth. Since several years, the study of human resource management methods has been a crucial component of management and organisational success, particularly in the banking industry. Human resource management techniques relate to organisational actions aimed at managing the organization's pool of human resources and ensuring that those resources are used effectively to accomplish organisational goals. As part of the liberalisation process, private banks were licenced. As a result, different banks have unique management imperatives and may employ a variety of human resource management approaches. Effective human resource management strategies assist organisations in attracting and retaining talent, training workers for tough jobs, growing their skills and competencies, boosting productivity and profitability, and improving overall quality of life.

Risk Management - As competition heats up, banks' competitiveness suffers. The

global environment is continually posing threats to the Indian banking industry. Several foreign banks have already driven India's banking sector bankrupt. As a result, it is widely viewed as the most serious threat to the Indian financial sector.

Maintaining the Growth Pace- The banking business, like the rest of the economy, faces difficulties in maintaining the economy's growth pace. Workers are fully responsible for the banking industry's success, and employees are primarily concerned with themselves. Employee satisfaction is crucial to attaining and sustaining bank growth.

Human Resource Management- One of the most important needs in today's competitive environment is effective human resource management. Efficient human resource management necessitates solid managerial abilities in order to handle the human resource. As a result, human resource management is the most difficult task confronting the Indian banking industry.

Global Banking- It is impossible for any nation to remain isolated from the global economy. For long-term growth, the integration process of liberalisation and globalisation, which India utilised in 1991, must be implemented. Furthermore, the effects of globalisation provide a problem for local companies, since they are forced to compete with global entities.

Employee Retention- Over the past 10 years, the banking sector has shifted fast from transactional and customer service-oriented to an increasingly cutthroat environment where revenue completion is the primary focus. Employees are getting dissatisfied with their long-term employment in the same business, and they are often hesitant to meeting new demands. Employee retention is becoming a major challenge for the banking sector at all levels.

Information Technology Revolution: - The problem of adjusting the workplace to fast technological advances that impact the nature of work and cause obsolescence is difficult; technology is the key to servicing all client groups. Because of the rising quality, flexibility, and complexity of product and service offerings, efficient use of technology is crucial for minimising business risks.

3. Literature Review

Human Resource Practices refers to the policies and procedures that govern the 'human resource (HR)' aspects of a

management position, such as human resource planning, job analysis, recruitment, selection, orientation, compensation, performance appraisal, training and development, and labour relations⁴. Human resource management encompasses the rules, methods, and processes that shape an employee's behaviour, attitude, and performance⁵. Human resource management techniques have an influence on an organization's employee performance and competitive advantage⁶. The Harvard Model, the Guest Model, and the Warwick Model. Among these approaches, the Guest Model of Human Resource Management is widely regarded as superior than the others⁷. The present study chose human resource practises such as institutional commitment and motivation, employee relations, compensation, physical work environment (tangibles), training and development, promotion, and job satisfaction that were incorporated and adopted from the Guest Model and the Society of Human Resource Management in the United States of America. Employee performance is critical for every business since it indicates the

⁴ Dessler, G., 2007. Human Resource Management, New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Private Limited.

⁵ Noe, R. A., Hollenbeck, J. R., Gerhart, B., Wright, P. M., 2007. Human Resource Management: Gaining a Competitive Advantage, USA: McGraw-Hill.

⁶ Kovach, K.A., 1987. What motivates employees? Workers and supervisors give different answers, Business Horizons, 30(5), pp: 58-65

⁷ Aswathappa, K., 2008. Human Resource Management: Text and Cases, Delhi: Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Limited

capacity of employees to accomplish goals as intended⁸, performance is highly dependent on perception, values, and attitudes. Porter and Lawler defined performance as the result of an individual's talent, skill, and effort in a certain setting. In other words, employee performance refers to an employee's capacity to operate effectively and efficiently in order to contribute to the achievement of corporate goals and objectives. Thus, for the sake of the study, the researchers define "employee performance" as the amount of effort that employee devotes to his or her work.⁹

This research will recommend acceptable human resource management strategies, policies, procedures, programmes, and practises, as well as potential results in bank contexts. The study enables an understanding of human resource management methods and employee performance in public sector banks, as well as the role of technology in retaining workers in today's competitive environment. The study assisted us in gaining an understanding of the existing techniques used by banks to manage their staff. The study contributes to the research conducted by policymakers and bankers, among others. Additionally, it would be used in the design of bank rules governing human resource management procedures in the banking industry. As a result, the current study focuses on human resource management techniques in public sector banks.

4. Objectives

The main purpose of the study is

1. To overview various HR practices affecting the employees performance
2. To measure the impact of the HR practices on the employees performance

5. Methodology

This Descriptive study is based on the sample of employee's workings in different banks. The data was collected by using questionnaire (Google form) The sample method used for the study was purposive sampling – 250 samples have been taken from the private sector banks in the study area.

6. Findings, Discussions and Results

The study is indented to study the different HR practices which are significantly influence on the performance of the bank employees and their impact on their performance. They are empirically analysed as below.

7. HR practices

The Human Resource Management is the key for bring out the excellence in the man power used in the organization. The efficiency through their practices is going to directly influence on their performance. This study considers various practices based on the previous studies and theoretical background. The opinion of the respondents about the practices is observed by using 5 point Likert scale. The result is shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: HR practices

Code	HR practices	Mean	Std. Deviation
HRP1	Training and Development	3.17	1.286

⁸ Awan, A. G., and Tahir, T. M., 2015. Impact of working environment on employee's productivity: A Case Study of Banks and Insurance Companies in Pakistan, *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(1), pp: 329-345.

⁹ Porter, L. W. and Lawler, E. E., 1974. The Effect of Performance on Job Satisfaction. In Edwin A. Fleishman *Studies in Personal and Industrial Psychology*. Third Edition, Illinois.

HRP2	Employee Engagement	3.10	1.088
HRP3	Competence	3.08	1.075
HRP4	Recognition	3.14	1.254
HRP5	Leadership	2.98	1.391
HRP6	Compensation	3.03	1.168
HRP7	Performance evaluation	3.11	1.101
HRP8	Workload	3.15	1.133

The above table shows that all the HR practices i.e., Training and Development (3.17), Employee Engagement (3.10), Competence (3.08), Recognition (3.14), Leadership (2.98), Compensation (3.03), Performance evaluation (3.11) and Workload (3.15) are having means 3 and above. It shows that the employees feel all the HR practices are done well in their banks. The employees' performance is based on the practices. The respondents are asked to mention about their opinion on the impact of each practice

influence on their performance. The impact is measured with the help of regression analysis.

Impact of HR practices on the performance

Before measuring the impact of the HR practices on the performance, inter relationship between the variables is studied with the help of correlation. The result is given below.

Table 2: Interrelationship between HR practices

Practices	HRP1	HRP2	HRP3	HRP4	HRP5	HRP6	HRP7	HRP8
HRP1	1.000							
HRP2	0.614	1.000						
HRP3	0.511	0.471	1.000					
HRP4	0.232	0.405	0.490	1.000				
HRP5	0.152	0.237	0.304	0.667	1.000			

HRP6	0.307	0.320	0.376	0.581	0.628	1.000		
HRP7	0.310	0.303	0.332	0.460	0.350	0.515	1.000	
HRP8	0.523	0.454	0.337	0.365	0.177	0.452	0.515	1.000
HRP1	0.000							
HRP2	0.000	0.000						
HRP3	0.000	0.000	0.000					
HRP4	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000				
HRP5	0.008	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000			
HRP6	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		
HRP7	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
HRP8	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000

The Table 2 shows that the relationship between all the HR practices is significant. The opinion of the respondents towards each practice of the HR department is significantly correlating each other. The result of the regression model representing

the influence of the various HR practices (predictors) on the performance of the employees (dependent variable). The following tables are the result of the model.

Table 3: Model summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.976 ^a	0.952	0.950	1.05301	1.371
a. Predictors: (Constant), HRP1, HRP2, HRP3, HRP4, HRP5, HRP6, HRP7 and HRP8					
b. Dependent Variable: Performance					

The R value (0.976) shows the contribution of the 8 practices on the performances of the employees. The R square value (0.952) indicates that the predictors contribute 95%

on the changes in the performance of the employees. It shows that the selected HR practices are contributing at a greater level.

Table 4: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5277.507	8	659.688	594.939	0.000 ^b
	Residual	267.229	241	1.109		
	Total	5544.736	249			
a. Dependent Variable: Performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant HRP1, HRP2, HRP3, HRP4, HRP5, HRP6, HRP7 and HRP8						

The result from the ANOVA is shows the calculated value of F (594.939) is highly significant for the degree of freedom 8.

The p value is 0.000 (significant at 1% level). It is concluded from the result the

model is fit and the coefficient of the variables can be analyzed further.

Table 5: Coefficients

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-0.912	0.269		-3.388	0.001
HRP1	1.121	0.075	0.305	14.856	0.000
HRP2	0.945	0.084	0.218	11.274	0.000
HRP3	1.237	0.081	0.282	15.192	0.000
HRP4	0.871	0.085	0.231	10.253	0.000
HRP5	0.848	0.073	0.250	11.677	0.000
HRP6	0.317	0.085	0.079	3.722	0.000
HRP7	-0.099	0.078	-0.023	-1.277	0.203
HRP8	0.038	0.081	0.009	0.472	0.637
Dependent Variable: Performance					

The Table 5 reveals that all the HR practices called Training and Development, Employee Engagement, Competence, Recognition, Leadership and Compensation are strongly influencing the performance of the employees. The t values are greater than 1.96 for these practices. Training and Development (14.856), Employee Engagement (11.274), Competence (15.192), Recognition (10.253), Leadership (11.677) and Compensation (3.722) are the significant at 1% level (p values are less than 0.01). Hence, it is concluded that practices of HR called Training and Development, Employee Engagement, Competence, Recognition, Leadership and Compensation are directly influencing the performance of the employees. It is suggested that the management may focus on these practices much as they contribute more on their employees' performance.

8. Conclusion

Human resource procedures are critical in firms want to improve employee performance. Organizations with consistent human resource practises and policies expect workers to view the job relationship as a long-term one involving a variety of elements. This work contributes to a growing corpus of research that aims to illuminate the black box by elucidating how, when, and to what degree human resource strategies effect employee

performance. Further study is needed to elucidate the distinctions between more broad-based measures of perceived performance and more targeted measures of more specific perceptions of financial or market-related success in connection to high-performance work practises. There are several more human resource practises that should not overlook since they are as critical and may be researched, including selection procedures, training techniques, appraisal practises, recruiting strategies, and development practises. The study concluded that practices of HR such as training and development, employee engagement, competence, recognition, leadership and compensation are directly influencing the performance of the employees. It is suggested that the management may focus on these practices much as they contribute more on their employees' performance.

9. Reference

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